

NEGOTIATING NICOSIA'S PUBLIC SQUARES: PLACE FORMATION ACROSS THE DIVIDE. A LOCAL PERSPECTIVE

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INTRODUCTION

Public squares are considered by many as pillars of social life, reflecting the quality and vivacity of interaction between citizens and acting as spaces for displays of power.

Nicosia makes an interesting case to explore public squares, as it is a city, and probably still the only capital in Europe, cut in two by a dividing line, a buffer zone. The first demarcation line separating the Greek from the Turkish sector of Nicosia was drawn in 1958 following the intercommunal violence that erupted during the anticolonial armed revolt. In 1964, following another round of intercommunal strife and now in an independent Cyprus, Turkish Cypriots retreated into a series of enclaves in the Turkish quarter in the northern part of the city, a move counteracted with an economic embargo so severe the United Nations reacted with protestations against the Republic of Cyprus (ROC) Government.¹ Additionally, with the intervention of the United Nations, Nicosia was divided into a Greek and Turkish sector; the existing dividing line was cemented and came to be known as “the Green Line”.² While the embargoes and restrictions to movement were lifted in 1968, Nicosia did not recover from the partition. On the contrary, the line extended across the entirety of the island in 1974.

The Green Line extends approximately 180 km across the island. In some parts of old Nicosia it is only a few meters wide, while in other areas it is a few kilometres wide, but neither side permits access to it. The period after the 1974 war not only divided the island geographically but affected all aspects of life, including the economic, social, and cultural development of the communities. The Republic of Cyprus continued to advance alongside the developed world, while the Turkish Cypriot community remained a de facto structure, unrecognised by the international community and only recognized by Turkey. The impact of the division became even more recognisable over time, influencing recognisable characteristics of the city across the divide.

Crossing to the “other side” of the city only became possible as late as 2003, 40 years after the establishment of the UN-Patrolled Green Line. This was a landmark in the history of the Cyprus problem: for the first time, people from the two communities could explore the “other side”, interact, exchange, and collaborate without a special permit from the United Nations, as had been the case up to then. Researchers observe that this has, over time, also reflected on the broadening scholarly emphasis on the Cyprus conflict and focus on ethnonationalism to a more diverse set of research topics, including labour migrants; the island’s religious and ethnic character; the environment and climate change; and the politics of resource extraction.³

This paper derives from a wider research project⁴ which attempts to investigate the transformation of the urban centre of Nicosia on three levels: demographics, business activity, and monument building in relation to certain political and socio-economic events that have shaped the history of Cyprus from 1960 until 2020 and, in this context, it discusses the evolution of three key public squares across the divide as focal points that tend to reflect change and are worthy of exploration.

Methodology

Cultural historians who have written about Nicosia and its squares are usually guided by their own recollections. These accounts, akin to autoethnographic scholarship, recount their memories of certain places, and they take ownership by transmitting their lived personal experiences. These accounts also validate local narratives through oral histories, adding an autoethnographic layer to place-making and history writing. The writings of Alev Adil that examine the northern part of the walled city of Nicosia, both as an academic observer and as a Nicosian, fall within this context and worked as an inspiration for us as well.⁵ Ellis and Bochner (2000) advocate autoethnography as a form of writing that makes ‘the researcher’s own experience a topic of investigation in its own right’⁶ instead of appearing to be ‘written from nowhere by nobody’.⁷ Autoethnography is not a flight from the rational or collective to the individual and emotional, but a demand we examine how both are interwoven.⁸ We are not claiming we have conducted autoethnographic research for the purposes of this paper, for this would have to include the appropriate methodology; we use our own observations to add another layer, a more local and personal one, to the historical data that backs up the transformation of the points of interest analysed here.

A biographical note should be added here. We are both Cypriots, one from the Turkish-Cypriot community, the other from the Greek-Cypriot community, approximately the same age, with different native tongues, one with studies in the history of art and the other in history. We have been experiencing Nicosia for decades but mostly half of the city, each, from the other side of the buffer zone, at least until 2003 when the crossings opened. Our experiences, observations, and memories are both similar and different. Therefore, in this case, we attempt to inject a historical project with our own personal experiences and standpoints by explaining a personal connection to the project or by using personal knowledge to help us in the research process.⁹

Pockets of history

Within a city, squares are living examples of spaces that mediate events and reflect change and memory.¹⁰ They can be considered pockets of history, or pockets of memory or, as Broto wrote, “the most emblematic urban space for the commemoration of history or government of a certain place.”¹¹ Academics have established the square is a place of geographic convergence and historic memory¹² which has some characteristics or criteria, both morphological-aesthetical¹³ and functional.¹⁴ Not all urban squares fulfil these criteria, however, as will be explained. Additionally, squares are not necessarily only linked to historical events or places of commemoration. They also have a more social dimension as places of conglomeration where diverse crowds gather. Indeed, the everyday social and cultural function of squares is a powerful harbinger of collective memory.

Atatürk Square

Atatürk Square, also known and more commonly referred to as Sarayönü Square, is the oldest locus of administration in the old city of Nicosia. In Turkish, Sarayönü means “the square in front of the palace”, a name given to the square for its proximity to the Lusignan Royal Palace.¹⁵ Although not the physical centre of the walled city, this area throughout history “was practically always counted and used as the belly [centre] of Nicosia,” where people gathered for festivities during religious holidays

(like Eid), funerals, parades, and open air markets.¹⁶ In addition to administrative buildings, residences and offices, the square was surrounded by other facilities with social and religious functions, like a hammam, a mosque and medrese, a church, as well as other gathering places like coffee houses.¹⁷ Its present name, Atatürk Square, was given to it March 1943 by the then Greek Cypriot mayor, Dr Themistoklis Dervis, right before the mayoral elections that same year, as a tactical move to gain the confidence and vote of the Turkish Cypriots. Naming the square for Ataturk is said to have contributed to the community's sense of ownership over the square.¹⁸

Figure 1. Photograph depicting Saray Square, Nicosia, 1945

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Over the years, the square maintained its importance for the Turkish-Cypriot community not only as a place for administration and commerce, but for cultural exchange and visibility. Located at the junction of Kyrenia Avenue and Sarayönü Street, the open area of the square allowed for different types of celebrations to take place, resulting in memorable experiences cited in published recollections. Writer-journalist Hizber Hikmetağalar offers a sentimental description of the square as a place of expression for the Turkish-Cypriot community: “We have always gathered in this area for all our bitter or sweet, angry or happy gatherings, our demonstrations and rallies in Sarayönü, our protests, we shouted our national existence to the world from here, and we passed our funerals through this square.”¹⁹

Figure 2. Funeral procession, 1957. Source: Tuncer Bagiskan Archive

The harmony of the square shifted during the mid-century with landscaping and the demolition of surrounding one-storey shops. Cultural historians have often cited the construction of high-rise buildings replacing the historic Ottoman-colonial architecture in the walled city as a loss,²⁰ while academics dubbed it as “a transformation both in terms of architecture and in terms of socio-cultural and political change.”²¹ Historical images, as documents of the (lost) past, give us a glimpse into such descriptions of the square. The Sarayönü Hotel (Figure 1), built in 1963 amidst conflict and limited resources, is a stark example of this, overpowering the square, and dwarfing the once dominant Venetian Column and the openness of its surroundings.

Figure 3. Abdullah Onar, Sarayönü Square, 1967, Watercolour on paper.

Source: Anber Onar archive

After 1960, several monuments symbolising and memorialising the struggle of the Turkish Cypriots experienced during the intercommunal conflict in the 1950s were erected in the northern part of the city. Among these was the figure of Kemal Atatürk. The first full-size figure of Atatürk was erected on 29 October 1963 in front of the Kyrenia Gate of Nicosia, after travelling slowly in a caravan from the port of Famagusta to the capital, during which thousands of Turkish Cypriots greeted the statue in celebration, throwing flowers.²²

*Figure 4. Film Still of Ataturk Statue unveiling.
Kyrenia Gate, Nicosia, 29 October 1963
Source: CyBC Archives*

Writing about the statue, artist and academic Mehmet Adil recalls the conflation of national identity with monument building and the construction of squares in the context of symbolic belonging: “Looking back, it seems that in our daily chores such images acted as constant mnemonic devices, reminding us that as a family we belonged to a larger Turkish family, the Turkish nation whose founder and father was Kemal Atatürk. This was not a matter that was ever explicitly discussed at home rather it was to be tacitly understood via the presence of such images. It was a matter of symbolic belonging.”²³

*Figure 5. Figure Statue of Dr. Fazıl Küçük, 27 January 1989
Statue Design: Tankut Öktem, Project Architect: Ali Semi
Photo credit: Authors.*

It was not until 1989 that the statue of Dr. Fazıl Küçük,²⁴ the political leader of Turkish Cypriots, would be erected near this site at İnönü Square, Kyrenia Gate, a square that would host the largest rally in 2004 to support the "yes" vote to the referendum held in response to the UN Annan Plan for the solution of the Cyprus problem.²⁵ Such monuments also echo that Atatürk Square and nearby İnönü Square are two squares that bear the traces of political life and that have become social symbols.²⁶

Faneromeni Square

Located within the walled city, Phaneromeni Square was once the commercial heart of Nicosia. Although used by the whole population, its premises showed a prominently Greek character, mainly due to the Greek Orthodox Panagia Phaneromeni church, from which the square takes its name, which has stood in the middle of the square since 1873. Opposite the church there's an imposing school of neoclassical architecture (1897) and the Mausoleum of Archbishop Kyprianos, the cleric who was hanged during the Greek revolution of 1821. A small Ottoman minaret that stands between the school and the church testifies to the city's Ottoman past, like many other Ottoman buildings in the walled city. Both the Church and the school predefined the character of the square which, due to its spacious form, became the ideal place for formal manifestations of the Greek Orthodox identity, especially after WWII. Commemorations for Greece's national day usually culminated there; the official name

of the square is “28th October square”, a commemoration of Greece’s entry into WWII against the Axis powers.

From the 1960s onwards, and especially after 1974, political tension and lack of stability, combined with the loss of land across the divide, led to the formation of new communities and housing complexes in the suburbs.²⁷ The old city was gradually abandoned by the Greek-Cypriot population. Indicatively, according to the 2001 census, there were 129 Greek-Cypriot residents at Faneromeni and 383 non-Greek Cypriots.²⁸ The regression probably culminated at the end of 1980s and the beginning of 1990s, when many shops near the buffer zone had to close for business due to limited traffic.

Interestingly, during this time the area around the square became inhabited mainly by non-Greek Cypriots of limited financial means who lived in poor conditions. This is attributed to a law passed in the 1990s which allowed third-country nationals to work in Cyprus, a move that significantly changed the labour market and affected the demographic character of the city.²⁹ Gradually, the area’s demographic character became very multicultural, as testified by the Faneromeni primary school and the nearby kindergarten, which accommodate mostly children of immigrants.³⁰ The presence of immigrants gave a new life to the old city, though the local population was usually described in derogatory terms, with many arguing the area was being transformed into a “ghetto of foreigners and commercial misery”.³¹

Figure 6&7. Faneromeni Square today ©Deputy Ministry of Tourism

Against this background, Faneromeni square seemed unable to play its social role and encourage the mingling of people from diverse backgrounds and social strata. While, it ostensibly had Siite’s morphological criteria of an urban square,³² it still failed to accommodate the population living in the area. Towards the end of the decade, and especially after the opening of the Ledra Street crossings in 2008 and the beginning of the works in Eleftheria Square, Faneromeni Square gained some momentum, although this is not reflected in the volume of business activity, which remained more or

less the same until 2020.³³ Independent coffee shops and restaurants appeared in the Square, however, which were frequented by younger people who preferred the area over the more mainstream and commercial establishments outside the walls; the square was also used for festivals, charity markets and other events. While during the weekends Greek Cypriots frequented the square for leisure, in essence the square had become a multicultural place, and as a Greek-Cypriot resident said, “the only place in Cyprus where you have [...] everything coexists harmoniously. It's full of life, as a square should be.”³⁴ Recently, the Church agreed to the conversion of the school into the Architectural School of the University of Cyprus, a decision that caused a stir within civil society as to whether such a move will lead to the gentrification or rehabilitation of the area.

Eleftheria Square

At the other end of the old city lies Eleftheria Square (Freedom Square), which admittedly does not fulfil the requirements of a proper square; architecturally it is in fact a bridge, rather than a square, and as such it functioned until recently. It was one of the first openings in the walled city which allowed access to the area outside the walls, then possible only through the three original Gates of Nicosia's Venetian walls.³⁵ In the 1940s and 1950s the square gained popularity due to its proximity to the commercial streets nearby, and the entertainment options it offered, such as cinemas, theatres, and cafés. This continued for some time later, until the mid-1970s when, after the war, a large part of the population tried to rebuild their lives outside the urban centre. The square was for decades the focal point for rallies against colonial rule, the coup and the war in 1974, for mass political assemblies,³⁶ and for celebrations such as that for the accession of Cyprus into the EU in 2004.

Figure 8. Photograph depicting Eleftheria Square, Nicosia, 1990

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For many years, many efforts for the reconstruction of the square took place, but the one that eventually bore fruit provoked ambivalence. Zaha Hadid's impressive architectural design was considered foreign to the city's historical character and built heritage. The design could not change, but people's intervention was decisive as to the functionality of the square, for they persuaded the authorities to decide against the use of cars in the renovated square, a break from its use as a passage for more than 100 years: "The Public Square, as an important part of the urban fabric of an urban

centre, is the place where the citizen will escape from his everyday life, where the artist will exhibit works of art, where the elderly, the disabled, will socialize. It is the place where each of us will enjoy moments of relaxation, where we will attend events, festivals, celebrations. [...] The square, by definition, offers security, relaxation, rest. It is not divided to allow the passage of vehicles. Then it would be called ‘road’, or ‘avenue’”.³⁷ Further to this, a lighted projection on the Jean Nouvel building that overlooks the square, saying “Square, not road,” made an imposing visual manifestation of public sentiment.

Figure 9. Eleftheria Square today, ©Nicosia Municipality

Figure 10. Eleftheria Square © Ο Φιλελεύθερος 13 March 2017

CONCLUSION

City squares can be a good example of how public spaces are affected by the course of history and societal changes. The look we took into these three public squares across the dividing line in Nicosia helps us realise these places are experienced differently by different people, over time serving different needs or failing to do so. As the green line sits comfortably across the heart of the city, we wonder what stories will be told standing at the top of the Saray Hotel or the Jean Nouvel building; what would we see from which views?

Since the establishment of the Republic and the developments we have briefly described, Nicosia has undergone major transformations which have become very visible in the open areas of the city, too, and more specifically in the central public squares. Although the city is enveloped within the uniformity of the city's Venetian walls, in Nicosia the past is seen and remembered differently across this divide. The urban development of the city centre, occurring at different paces, reflects these discrepancies and conflicting histories, forming detached visions that cater to different objectives, which are many times unaligned with the public's behavioural formations and social needs.

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